

On the Concept of Philosophical Contradiction

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Abstract: The existing textbook "Basic Principles of Marxism" adopts the way of "getting straight to the point" when explaining the connotation of contradictory concepts. This will confuse many students and is not conducive to their understanding. As an important concept, contradiction has different meanings in different situations and contexts. Contradiction is divided into original meaning and extended meaning. Comparative analysis of different types of contradictory concepts and identification in comparison are helpful for students to deepen their understanding and grasp of philosophical contradictions.

Keywords: rhetorical contradiction; the contradiction of a sick sentence; Contradictions in everyday life; Formal logic contradiction; Dialectic logical contradiction

I. Introduction

The existing textbook "Basic Principles of Marxism" (Higher Education Press 2021 Edition, hereinafter referred to as "Principles" textbook) uses a "straight to the point" approach when explaining the connotation of the concept of contradiction: contradiction is a philosophical category that reflects the unity of opposites within and between things. On the whole, there is no problem for the textbook to explain the contradictory meanings with this concise expression. However, for many college students, especially those who studied science in high school, when they first came into contact with the concept of contradiction, they would have a kind of confusion: why is this contradiction not in the same channel as the contradiction in our daily life?

It is not surprising that students have such doubts, because they think that philosophical contradictions are the same as contradictions in everyday life, and that they are "on the same channel". But the fact is that the two "channels are different", because the concept of contradiction itself has "many channels", just as we "CCTV" has many channels. The author humbly listened to many peers' lectures. When talking about philosophical contradictions, although most of the teachers expanded the content of the textbook and said that philosophical contradictions were different from those in daily life, most of the teachers simply compared the contradictions in "contradictions" with philosophical contradictions and briefly pointed out the differences between the two. It was not explained to the students that there was a contradiction of "other channels". In this way, students are more likely to think that the conflict is only two "different channels".

So how many channels are there? Hegel, the German modern dialectic master, once said that the noun or concept we often hang on to is often the thing we know the least about. Contradiction belongs to such a noun or concept. As the basic elements of Chinese language, nouns or concepts have different meanings in different scenes and contexts. In order to guide students to better study philosophical contradictions and understand the characteristics of philosophical contradictions, it is necessary for us to compare and analyze different types of contradictory concepts, analyze and identify them in comparison, and deepen the understanding and grasp of philosophical contradictions in the identification.

1.1 The original meaning of contradiction

The original meaning of contradiction is spear and shield. Spear and shield are two kinds of weapons with different functions in ancient times. A spear is a spear with a bronze or iron tip at one end of a long rod. Shield, a weapon used to protect the body from swords and spears, usually in round and square shapes. Spear and shield, as ancient weapons of war, are both opposites and unified. The opposites are shown in that their functions are completely opposite, spear is used for attack, shield is used for defense, which reflects their opposites or differences. Unity: Spear and shield united in one soldier. Soldiers practice or fight with a spear in one hand and a shield in the other, so as to achieve the purpose of attacking in defense and defending in attack.

II. The extension of contradiction

On the basis of long-term practice of social life, due to the needs of academic research and expression, people gradually expand and enlarge the original meaning of contradiction, and extend some other meanings, resulting in the extended meaning of contradiction. The extended meaning of contradiction can be roughly divided into five basic types. These five kinds of contradictions include both philosophical and non-philosophical contradictions. Understanding of non-philosophical contradictions helps us to draw a clear line between philosophical contradictions and non-philosophical contradictions in the process of distinction and comparison, so as to prevent confusion of thinking caused by mixing them together.

2.1 The first kind of contradiction is called rhetorical contradiction. Well, then, anywhere means to go against anything. It is a kind of figure of speech. It was first put forward in the book *New Style of Rhetoric*, edited by Tan Yong xiang (Fujian Education Publishing House, 1983.10).

This figure of speech is to negate all and then affirm some, or to affirm all and then deny some in order to highlight and emphasize the role of the latter part. The so-called "misalignment" means that something is both wholly positive and partly negative, or both wholly negative and partly positive. Positive, is to foil, emphasize the negative part; Negation is to set off and emphasize the positive part. This is a figure of speech whose name is rarely known. In daily life, people often use the rhetorical devices of mutual misfortunes, such as "everyone is here, but Xiao Ming is absent".

Other typical examples are:

(1) "Everything is inferior, only reading high." (First deny all, then confirm some, extremely strong

emphasis on the importance of reading.)

(2) "Everything is ready except the east wind." (Affirming all of them and then denying some of them, strongly demonstrating the importance of the east wind.)

(3)"Just to the door, I saw Aunt Zhao and Aunt Zhou two people to look at Baoyu. Baoyu and the others all stood up and sat down, but Sister Feng alone ignored them." (" A Dream of Red Mansions "sixth chapter) (Here highlight the difference of Sister Feng.)

(4) "For more than a decade, I learned again. I learned how to cook, how to be a hostess among the guests, how to do everything. I could not attribute his success to my success." (Xu Zhongpei, "Contradictions")

(5) Idiom: Nothing like it.

(6)"There was no one in the room except the baby." (Shi Entrench Officials by Du Fu)

(7)"The world is cloudy and I am alone. Everyone is drunk and I am alone." (Records of the Grand Historian, The Biography of Qu Yuan)

(8)"If I were a philosopher, I would think, what does this turn symbolize? Is it telling a truth? If I were a poet, how poetic this turn is, I would surely make a graceful poem. I'm nothing but a wanderer. Not a homecoming, but a traveler." (Nameless "South Crossing River Water Bend")

(9) Brain platinum advertising slogan: "This year the Chinese New Year does not receive gifts, gifts only receive brain platinum." (If the two rhetoric are used together, the effect is remarkable.)

(10) I looked at my father's nose, and looked at my uncle's nose, and said to him: "Uncle, you and dad everywhere like, is not like a little." (My Uncle Lu Xun)

This kind of rhetorical contradiction is what we should learn, master and apply.

2.2 The second kind of contradiction, the contradiction of sentence nature: semantic expression before and after conflict, unable to justify itself, inexplicable. Such as:

(1) One evening morning, a young old man, riding on a black white horse, with a sharp dull knife in his hand, killed his dear enemy. The blind man saw it and told the deaf, the deaf told the dumb and the lame, and the lame picked up the dumb and ran quickly to the police station to report it. The police responded to the crime in a hurry and a slow drive in a brand new beat-up car, down the straight road 99 turns, finally arrived at the scene...

(2) When asked by a reporter, an old man proudly said, I lived for over 100 years in the 20th century.

This kind of paradoxical sentence often occurs when people do not consider properly. Therefore, when writing and expressing, we should think clearly, think carefully, develop rigorous writing habits and expression habits, and strive to avoid such mistakes.

2.3 The third type of conflict is the conflict in everyday life: the difference of opinions or behaviors between individuals or groups. Such as:

(1) In the matter of filling out the college entrance examination, the daughter and her father have a conflict: the daughter is interested in literature and wants to apply for the Chinese department of Normal University, while the father thinks that she should apply for the finance department of the University of Finance and Economics, so as to get a good job after graduation.

(2) At the end of the Qin Dynasty, the ruling class levied excessive taxes on the common people, increased

taxes and corvee labor, which led to unhappiness and discontent among the people. The conflict between the peasant class and the feudal ruling class reached an irreconcilable level.

Such differences and conflicts are what we need to recognize and resolve.

2.4 The fourth kind of contradiction, formal logic contradiction: that is, the contradiction that violates the three basic laws of formal logic (identity, law of contradiction and law of exclusion).

(1) Contradiction that violates identity. Identity is one of the basic laws of formal logic, its content is: in the same correct thinking process, each thought is the same as itself. That is to say, in the same thinking process, concepts and judgments must be used in the same sense and cannot be used in different senses. Logical errors that violate this requirement are called "confusing concepts" or "stealing concepts." For example:

Of all things in the world, man is the first precious.

I'm human.

Therefore, I am the first of all things precious.

In this reasoning, the "person" in the two premises is not the same concept. The first "man" is a set concept, and the second "man" is a non-set concept, so the mistake of "confusing the concept" or "stealing the concept" is made.

(2) A contradiction that violates the law of contradiction (also called the law of non-contradiction). Two conflicting or opposite propositions cannot be true at the same time; one of them must be false. Such as the idiom story "self-contradiction" in the "contradiction". The hero of "Contradiction" boasts that the spear in his hand is the sharpest spear in the world, and no matter how strong a shield is, it can pierce it; One side boasted that the shield in his other hand was the strongest in the world, and no spear, however sharp, could pierce it. So the question is, what happens if you poke the strongest shield with the sharpest spear? One, the spear pierced the shield, and the spear was the sharpest; Result two, the spear did not pierce the shield, the shield is the strongest. "The sharpest spear" and "the strongest shield" are two conflicting propositions, they cannot be true at the same time, one must be false.

(3) Conflicts that violate the law of exclusion. Two conflicting or opposite propositions cannot be false at the same time, and one of them must be true. The logical error that violates this requirement is often called "two cannot", that is, the negation of both propositions which contradict each other.

The Book of Mojing says, "Neither can be neither." For example, "Either is an ox, or a non-ox, neither can be neither."

"To say that there are ghosts in the world is superstition, but I disagree. But to say that there are no ghosts, I don't agree, because some phenomena are difficult to explain." This argument is "two can't". It negates both the contradictory propositions of "there are ghosts in the world" and "there are no ghosts in the world" at the same time, which violates the law of exclusion from the middle.

This kind of formal logic contradiction is what we should analyze and distinguish in order to get the correct

reasoning result.

2.5 The fifth kind of contradiction, dialectical logic contradiction: the contradiction in the philosophical sense, that is, the relationship between things and things is both opposite and unified.

Philosophical contradiction is the contradiction of objective existence, which is the correct reflection of the existence state of objective things. It is different from the subjective contradiction caused by the confusion of subjective thinking (such as the second kind of contradiction mentioned above). The key point to understand and grasp the philosophical contradiction is "both opposition and unity", or "unity of opposites". Here are some examples to illustrate:

(1)"The most familiar stranger." Singer Siu Ya-xuan once sang a song called The Most Familiar Stranger. At that time, the song became popular throughout the country with its well-known beautiful melody and became a representative work of Xiao Yaxuan. It will be between the hero and heroine from acquaintance, love (the most familiar) to break up and meet again (strange) emotional process interpretation of sad and yet beautiful, but also the hero and heroine after breaking up and meet again when the complex feelings show just right. For both men and women, they are familiar with each other first and then unfamiliar, both familiar and unfamiliar, "familiar" and "unfamiliar" are opposite and unified, and in a special situation and organic integration, unity as a whole.

(2)"Night and Day". First of all, day and night are opposites. Daytime refers to the period of time from dawn to dark. Night, refers to a period of time from dark to dawn. Secondly, "day" and "night" are complementary and unified. If there is only day and no night, the rest and growth rules of human beings and all kinds of other living things will be disrupted, the biological clock will be out of whack, causing a series of serious problems. The famous singer Na Ying has a song called "The day does not understand the darkness of the night", which tells people in an artistic way that the role of the night is extremely important and irreplaceable. If there is only night and no day, it means there is no sun and sunlight, and all kinds of living things, including human beings, will suffer fatal effects, because everything depends on the sun to grow. Only when day and night are united on the basis of their respective functions can a meaningful and valuable full day (24 hours) be formed.

(3)"Teachers and students". On the one hand, teachers and students are opposites. Teachers are different from students and their roles are completely different. The former's main task is to teach, the latter's main task is to learn. On the other hand, teachers and students are unified in teaching activities and teaching process. If there are only teachers without students, teachers lose the object of education, they also lose the meaning of existence and value. If only students have no teachers, without the teacher's enlightenment education and step-by-step guidance, students will not be able to complete the task of learning. Once a student asked me why there was only "Teacher's Day" instead of "Student's Day". I said that if only from the perspective of the confrontation between teachers and students, there is no "student day". However, if viewed from the perspective of the unification of the two, teachers and students are dialectically unified and inseparable. The existence of teachers is because of the existence of students, so "Teachers' Day" is also "students' Day". After listening to my analysis, the student was very satisfied and thought that using the principle of the unity of opposites to explain the problem could make people suddenly see the light.

(4)"Real Hair wig." Real hair is the opposite of a wig. Real hair is the opposite of a wig. Real hair and wig can be unified. In the first case, due to professional needs, for example, many TV news anchors often wear brown wigs on their own hair (real hair) in order to achieve better camera effect and news broadcast effect, so that the "real hair wig" is unified on the female anchors. In the second case, some people with thin or white hair often buy wigs made of real hair and wear them to enhance their appearance and boost their social confidence before attending important events or socializing.

III. What is the proper name for the fundamental attribute of philosophical contradiction

We cannot talk about philosophical contradictions without talking about their basic properties. The first problem to be solved when discussing the basic properties of philosophical contradictions is how to name the basic properties of philosophical contradictions appropriately. The basic attributes of philosophical contradiction are named as "contentiousness" and "identity" in the existing textbook of "Principles". The author thinks that it is more accurate and reasonable to use "opposition" and "unity" to name the basic attribute of contradiction than "contentiousness" and "identity". The reasons are as follows:

First of all, the "opposition" in the "opposites" and the "unity" in the "unity" are extracted from the connotation of the concept of contradiction (the relationship between opposites and unity within things). "The opposition and unity respectively reflect the two basic attributes of contradiction." It is concise, reasonable and clear to use "opposites" and "unity" to express the basic attributes of contradiction, which is more reasonable in logic.

Secondly, we cannot simply understand "antagonism" as "fighting". "Opposites" refers to "opposites" or "opposites" and can be used to refer to two things that are completely different or have opposite properties (functions). For example, we can say that "day and night" have opposites, they are only opposite in nature (function), they are two different phenomena, but can not say that there is a conflict between them. If there is a struggle, then why is there a struggle between "day and night"? How is it fought? Who wins and who loses the result of the struggle? Is it equal or equal? Obviously, these questions are unanswerable, and the reason for this unanswerable consequence is the one-sided understanding of "antagonism" as "conflict".

Of course, "antagonism" and "belligerence" also have a certain connection. "Opposites" can be converted into "contentions" under certain conditions, just as "potential energy" in physics can be converted into "kinetic energy" under certain conditions. The conflict between the two sides of a contradiction is built on the basis of opposition. Without opposition, there can be no struggle, but with "opposition", there may not be "conflict". The two opposing sides can live in peace and even harmony, reaching a state of "harmony without difference".

Third, by referring to the Modern Chinese Dictionary (2015 Edition of the Commercial Press), we can see that there is no difference between the meaning of "unity" and "same", and the two can be used interchangeably. Therefore, there is no difference between "unity" and "identity" in connotation. Since there is no difference, it is not necessary to substitute "identity" for "unity". In addition, from the frequency and number of these two words appear, "unity" is significantly higher than "identity", "identity" is not common. It is easy to understand and easy to understand, with popularity and affinity. Instead of the contradictory "identity", it is not only a little

unfamiliar, a little distant and strange in understanding, but also may mislead beginners, making them mistake "same" as "exactly the same".

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